

Predicting Resources for AI Workloads in HPC: Methods, Challenges, and Opportunities

1stSwathi Vallabhajosyula
The Ohio State University
Columbus, Ohio, USA
vallabhajosyula.2@buckeyemail.osu.edu

2nd Rajiv Ramnath
The Ohio State University
Columbus, Ohio, USA
ramnath.6@osu.edu

Abstract—Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming scientific discovery and industrial applications, but its growth has escalated demands on high-performance computing (HPC) resources. A central challenge is predicting resource requirements for deep neural network (DNN) workloads, where inefficient provisioning leads to underutilized GPUs, wasted CPUs, and higher costs. This work explores AI resource prediction in HPC using complementary approaches: Black-Box models leverage tabular features and regressors such as XGBoost for fast, workload-specific predictions. In contrast, White-Box models extract graph-based features from High-Level Optimized (HLO) graphs to generalize across architectures. Results show hybrid methods significantly improve accuracy, reducing fit-time estimation error from 75.48% to 10.55%. The estimators are being integrated with AI-driven job schedulers to improve workload allocation and utilization, paving the way for creating agents for Machine Learning Workflow (MLOps) systems across the computing continuum.

Index Terms—Artificial Intelligence, High-Performance Computing, Resource Prediction, Deep Neural Networks, Runtime Estimation, Energy-Aware Scheduling, MLOps, Inference Workloads, Edge Deployment, Sustainable AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has gained popularity over the past few years and continues to scale rapidly due to its adaptability to diverse domains and the increased availability of high-performance computing (HPC) hardware. This accessibility has enabled the use of AI-driven applications in areas once limited by the need for highly skilled engineers to design and maintain complex, domain-specific workflows that typically do not generalize.

Among AI subfields, computer vision (CV) stands out as one of the most widely adopted and mature domains, supported by a wealth of state-of-the-art models and pre-trained architectures. A major advantage of CV is that domain experts can often deploy these models “as is” or apply fine-tuning with modest amounts of domain-specific data, rather than reinventing entirely new architectures for each application. For instance, object detection models like YOLO (You Only Look Once) [5] can be readily adapted for human intrusion detection in wildlife ecology or for weed detection in agriculture, tasks that traditionally required extensive manual labor and time.

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This reusability and adaptability make CV an accessible entry point for non-AI specialists, lowering barriers to adoption across scientific and applied domains.

Although AI provides automation, scalability, precision, and consistency, along with broader challenges such as interpretability, ethical considerations, domain-specific constraints, bias, and explainability, it is also essential to address core implementation challenges to build long-term sustainable AI workflows. These include analyzing and estimating execution feasibility, costs, and resource requirements such as power, memory, CPU/GPU hours, storage, and bandwidth in shared HPC environments. Accurate resource prediction can improve scheduling, reduce queuing delays, minimize waste, and lower operational costs.

II. FROM WHO TO HOW: THE 6WS OF PREDICTING RESOURCES FOR AI WORKLOADS

Who? Researchers in a wide variety of disciplines, including biology, physics, agriculture, and climate science, are increasingly adopting artificial intelligence to accelerate discovery. However, many lack the expertise to configure complex HPC environments efficiently. This mismatch results in suboptimal resource usage and long job delays, making intelligent resource prediction a shared necessity for both HPC providers and end users.

What? The focus of this study is on predicting runtime and memory requirements for DNN workloads in HPC systems. [2] The current analysis of an OSC cluster ¹ shows severe inefficiencies: GPU utilization rarely exceeds 50% (mean ~23%), GPU memory averages only 12%, and CPU/RAM usage often remains below 20%. Poor provisioning strategies drive these inefficiencies strategies, for example, using high-end A100 GPUs for jobs that could run on V100s, or reserving entire nodes with 80 CPUs and 4 GPUs while leaving most CPUs idle. [4]

When? This problem is urgent. By 2030, AI workloads are projected to triple U.S. data center power consumption ². Addressing inefficient provisioning now is critical for sustainable AI growth, energy-aware HPC operations, and cost-effective deployment at scale.

¹The Ohio Supercomputer Center <https://www.osc.edu/>

²<https://www.energy.gov/articles/doe-releases-new-report-evaluating-increase-electricity-demand-data-centers>

Fig. 1. Overview of the HARP framework showing hybrid estimators, data curation, scheduler integration, and rule-based orchestration across the AI workflow lifecycle.

Where? The challenge arises in shared HPC environments where multiple users compete for limited CPU and GPU resources. Systems like the Ohio Supercomputer Center (OSC) and the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) represent environments where job scheduling inefficiencies directly impact research productivity, energy use, and operational budgets.

Why? Building domain-specific hardware or customized job schedulers for every AI workload is impractical and expensive. Instead, tailoring AI runtime configurations to available hardware is a more sustainable strategy. Accurate resource prediction enables better scheduling, reduces execution costs, and ensures fair resource sharing, supporting both individual researchers and the broader HPC community.

How? We propose two complementary approaches for DNN resource prediction:

- 1) **Black-Box Prediction:** Treats DNN training code as a closed job submitted to HPC. Features include hardware specifications, hyperparameters, input metadata, and handcrafted descriptors. Models such as XGBoost provide fast, application-specific predictions. Limitation: requires extensive training data and struggles to generalize to unseen architectures.
- 2) **White-Box Prediction:** Extracts graph-based features from High-Level Optimized (HLO) graphs, avoiding handcrafted features and improving generalization to new architectures. Limitation: requires hardware-specific feature extraction and incurs additional overhead.

Findings: The models were trained using execution profiles collected from TensorFlow applications, specifically focusing on convolutional neural networks (CNNs). These training profiles captured runtime characteristics such as CPU/GPU

utilization, memory footprint, and execution time, providing the necessary data to develop and validate the predictive models. With sufficient training data, XGBoost (Black-Box) achieves a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 10%, outperforming GNN-based models (13.54%). In data-scarce settings, a hybrid pipeline combining GNN and XGBoost reduces MAPE for fit-time estimation from 75.48% to 10.55%. (refer Table I) These results demonstrate that integrating black-box and white-box approaches provides a balanced hybrid framework capable of improving accuracy when the training data is limited. By embedding predictive intelligence into the scheduling layer [3] as shown in Figure 1, this research extends beyond making static estimations by integrating with a decision-making system that can adapt to workload dynamics at HPC centers and queuing configurations.

III. FUTURE WORK

A natural extension of this framework is to extend beyond training at the center to include inference at both the center and edge. The methodology can be adapted to estimate inference time by replacing training runtime (forward pass, gradient computation, and backpropagation) with only the forward pass of deployed models. This flexibility enables HPC systems to optimize both training and serving pipelines.

Furthermore, the framework can be adapted for edge inference scenarios by replacing HPC hardware features with those of edge devices. In this context, the estimator can predict power consumption, memory requirements, allocation utilization (from CPU and GPU usage), and bandwidth requirements, providing domain scientists with actionable insights on how and when to deploy AI models at the edge. For example, it can guide decisions on whether to run a lightweight animal detector on a drone versus a full species classification pipeline on an edge server, while also analyzing cost/latency trade-offs between edge and center-based processing.

By extending resource prediction from HPC training to inference and edge deployment, this framework lays the foundation for a unified system that supports sustainable AI across the full lifecycle of model development and deployment. Future work will focus on refining hybrid prediction methods, incorporating energy-aware scheduling, and enabling agentic systems for MLOps that can make intelligent decisions about when and where to execute workloads across edge and HPC environments.

TABLE I
MODEL COMPARISON FOR RESOURCE PREDICTION

Model	Type	Target	Data	MAPE (%)
Random Forest	BB	Seen	10K	3.7
XGBoost	BB	Seen	10K	1.63
Graph NN	WB	Seen	10K	11.16
Random Forest	BB	Unseen	10K	87.96
XGBoost	BB	Unseen	10K	10.00
Graph NN	WB	Unseen	10K	13.54
XGBoost	BB	Unseen	2K	77.29
Graph NN	WB	Unseen	2K	75.48
XGBoost + Graph NN	Hybrid	Unseen	2K	10.55

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